

The Effect of the Employee Information System Implementation on User Satisfaction Mediated by Internet Facilities at PT Kemajuan Industrindo Malang

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Abstract:- This study aims to describe the implementation of the personnel information system at PT Kemajuan Industrindo, analyze the effect of the implementation of the personnel information system on user satisfaction of PT Kemajuan Industrindo, and analyze the effect of the implementation of the personnel information system on user satisfaction mediated by internet facilities at PT Kemajuan Industrindo. The sample in this study was 67 respondents as employees who worked at PT Kemajuan Industrindo. This study is using a path analysis technique. The results of the analysis show that the implementation of the personnel information system affects user satisfaction, this means that the implementation of a staffing information system that is getting better and developing will have an impact on the satisfaction of information system users. Internet facilities can mediate between the implementation of staffing information systems to the satisfaction of information system users, this means that with the implementation of information systems implanted in internet facilities getting better and the development of internet facilities, it will have an impact on information system user satisfaction. And The implementation of staffing information systems to user satisfaction mediated by internet facilities has a dominant influence on the satisfaction of information system users.

Keywords:- Implementation of Personnel Information System, Internet Facilities, User Satisfaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of information technology can provide convenience to all levels of society to facilitate life, both in individual community life and professional community life. Along with the development of technology, now information technology can be accessed from basic interests to high-level interests. Information becomes an important element in human activity. Information systems that are not well integrated will have implications for things that are not following the purpose of the system. (Putri & Helfasari, 2019) Information technology can also be used to encourage companies to implement practical *Supply Chain Management* to optimize performance in the organization. (Ardianto et al., 2013) Information systems are a combination

of information technology and human activities to support operations and management. The information system serves to assist in the processing of data and convey information to its users based on calculations or a database that has been integrated into the information system. (Sukanto & Shalahuddin, 2015) According to (Raymond McLeod, 2001) "The quality of an information system implementation consists of 3 things, namely: accurate, timeliness and relevance". The rapid and rapid development of the internet requires organizations to develop and innovate to create breakthroughs. The Internet demands developments in the delivery of information, so it can be felt that today's organizations need a system that is fast and easily accessible online (anywhere and anytime) so that it can always provide real-time/up-to-date data. (Aini et al., 2017)

A system that is built manually and conventionally such as correspondence such as the stage of applying for permits to reporting extends the flow of data recording so that it buys work time. Information systems that run online are much better than conventional systems so that they can increase effectiveness and efficiency in achieving targets. Based on the phenomenon that occurs, the researcher wants to research PT Kemajuan Industrindo which is a company engaged in the agricultural machinery & construction industry located in Malang City, precisely on Irian Jaya Street No.17, Sukoharjo, Klojen, Malang, Indonesia. PT Kemajuan Industrindo Malang was established in 1962. From its establishment in 1962 until 2018 PT Kemajuan Industrindo has stored employee archives manually using a ledger containing employee data. Entering 2019 PT Kemajuan Industrindo began to use an information system implemented in a Local Area Network (LAN), PT Kemajuan Industrindo provides a computer that employees can use interchangeably to access information systems. However, this hampered the work process at PT Kemajuan Industrindo which was caused by queues due to the length of each employee's process of accessing the information system. In 2020 PT Kemajuan Industrindo migrated the personnel information system to the Internet network. To determine the level of satisfaction of information system users, PT Kemajuan Industrindo needs a measuring instrument to find out whether the implementation of information systems through internet facilities can increase user satisfaction of

staffing information systems for employees of PT Kemajuan Industrindo

Based on these conditions, the researcher wants to conduct research with a quantitative type by providing a questionnaire on how to satisfy employees of PT Kemajuan Industrindo after the implementation of the Personnel Information System. Quantitative research methods are research methods based on the philosophy of positivism, this research is used to examine certain populations or samples. Sampling techniques in this study are generally carried out randomly, data collection uses research instruments, and data analysis is quantitative/statistical to test predetermined hypotheses. (Sugiyono, 2015).

A. The Purpose of Research

Based on the formulation of the problem, the first purpose of this study is to find out the description of the implementation of the personnel information system, internet facilities, and user satisfaction at PT Kemajuan Industrindo. The second objective of this study is to analyze the effect of information system implementation on user satisfaction at PT Kemajuan Industrindo Malang. The third objective of this study is to analyze the effect of the implementation of the personnel information system on internet facilities at PT Kemajuan Industrindo. The fourth objective of this study is to analyze the effect of internet facilities on user satisfaction at PT Kemajuan Industrindo. The fifth objective of this study is to analyze the effect of the implementation of the personnel information system on the satisfaction of users through internet facilities at PT Kemajuan Industrindo.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Information System

Information System is a system in an organization that functions to bring together the needs of daily transaction processing that can support the function of managerial organizational operations with strategic activities for an organization to provide the information needed for decision-making for outsiders and certain parties (Oktaviani, 2019). The information system in the organization/company serves to provide information in detail against all levels of the organization and can be accessed at any time as long as such information is required. (Hidayatullah et al., 2021) According to (Raymond McLeod, 2001) "The quality of the implementation of an information system depends on 3 things: (1) *accurate*, (2) *timelines*, and (3) *relevance*". An information system is expected to be able to be accessed quickly, and accurately and have relevant results.

B. Internet Facilities

Along with the development of technology and the digital era, the internet and websites have become a necessity for individuals, organizations, companies, and government agencies. This happens because of the large needs of the world for the internet and *websites*. (Maharani et al., 2021). According to (Iqbal Kurniansyah & Sinurat, 2020a) The components of internet facilities are divided into 3, namely: (1) *Hosting* (2) *Domains*, and (3) *WebServers*. The increase in the number of web applications embedded in the hosting

should be followed by an increase in the quality of resources, especially when more performance is needed on the web service (Bik, 2017)

C. User Satisfaction

User satisfaction is a level of feeling of a user that is used as a result of a comparison between user expectations of the product and the real results obtained by users from the product (Kotler, 2009). User satisfaction is a cognitive situation of a purchase that is related to whether or not it is compatible with the results obtained which are compared with the sacrifices made by consumers. (Sisharini et al., 2019) According to (Harianto Respati, 2013) Building, consumer or customer trust with the accurate distribution of information can satisfy information system users based on the perception of the use of the information system. User satisfaction according to (Handiwidjojo & Ernawati, 2016) five aspects are considered the most dominant in the study of user satisfaction with information systems, including 1) Learnability 2) Efficiency 3) Memorability 4) Errors and Safety 5) Satisfaction.

D. The Employee Information System Implementation towards User Satisfaction Mediated by Internet Facilities

According to (Frisdayanti, 2019) stated that there are 3 important components in achieving user satisfaction and company success in the implementation of information systems: the three assets are human resources, asset technology, and relationships commonly known as *The three information technology assets*. The Internet is a network that can improve the field of technological assets. In this study, the researcher referred to an earlier study entitled *The Impact of Cloud-Based Information Systems Organization's Performance* (Algrari, 2017) The results of such studies are the results of path analysis showing that: The indirect influence of the application of information through *cloud-based* (internet facilities) on user satisfaction is the most effective influence and the most dominant influence. Increasing user satisfaction with information systems is more effective through the internet or *cloud-based* facilities because the results of indirect influence are greater than direct influence.

III. METHOD

This research is a research based on the purpose of the study, researchers use causality research plans with quantitative techniques. The data were obtained using a questionnaire using five answer choices using a Likert scale filled out by respondents.

A. Population dan sample

In this study, researchers used census techniques. According to (Sugiyono, 2015) The census technique is a sample determination technique when all members of the population are used as samples. In this study, because the population was less than 100 respondents, the researcher took 100% of the total population at PT Kemajuan Industrindo as many as 67 respondents.

B. Hypothesis

Based on the formulation of the problem, the phenomenon, and the theoretical basis that has been presented here are four hypotheses:

- H1: The implementation of the personnel information system (X) has a positive and significant effect on user satisfaction (Y) at PT Kemajuan Industrindo.
- H2: The implementation of the personnel information system (X) has a positive and significant effect on Internet Facilities (Z) at PT Kemajuan Industrindo
- H3: Internet facilities (Z) have a positive and significant effect on User Satisfaction (Y) at PT Kemajuan Industrindo.
- H4: There is a significant influence between the implementation of the personnel information system (X) on job satisfaction (Y) mediated by internet facilities (Z) at PT Kemajuan Industrindo.

C. Analytical Methods

The data analysis technique in this study uses quantitative analysis, this technique is carried out after all data are obtained based on the results of the questionnaire using structural equation analysis with SPSS software. This study used path analysis to test the influence of mediation variables. Hypothesis development testing can be seen from the significant degree of quality relationships between variables with the following conditions: (1) If the probability the < 0.05 then there is a significant influence between the independent variables and the dependent variables, so the hypothesis is accepted. (2) If the probability of > 0.05 then there is no significant influence between the independent variables on the dependent variables, so the hypothesis is rejected. In this study, there was 1 independent variable, one mediation variable, and one dependent variable.

Figure 1:- Structural Equation Model
Source: data processed (2022)

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Results

➤ Uji Validitas Model

Testing in the path analysis to be able to find out whether the analysis is valid or not. Testing the validity of the model in the path analysis two indicators need to be seen, namely the coefficient of total determination (Rm^2). In this case, the coefficient of determination Rm^2 is equal to the interpretation of the coefficient of determination R^2 in regression analysis. In this case, the interpretation of the coefficient of determination (Rm^2) is the same as the coefficient interpretation of determination R^2 in regression analysis.

$$Rm^2 = 1 - Pe1^2 - Pe2^2 \dots \dots Pei^2$$

$$Pe1 = \sqrt{1 - R_1^2} = \sqrt{1 - 0,506} = 0,702$$

$$Pe2 = \sqrt{1 - R_2^2} = \sqrt{1 - 0,560} = 0,663$$

$$Rm^2 = 1 - (0.702)^2 - (0.439)^2$$

$$= 1 - (0.492) - (0.193)$$

$$= 1 - 0,905$$

$$= 0,905$$

➤ Regression Analysis

Based on the results of the calculations above, a total coefficient of determination value of 0.905 was obtained, showing the variation in data that can be explained in the research model, namely 90.5% or in other words, the information contained in the 90.5% data can be explained in the research model.

Variable	B	Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
Information System	0.539	0.711	8.155	0.000
Dependent Variable	= Internet Facility			
Constanta	= 18.232			
R	= 0.711			
R square (R ²)	= 0.506			
F	66.502			
Probability	0.000			
Line Equation I	Z = Py1X1 + e			
Result	Z = 0.711 + e			

Table 1: - Regression Model 1
Source: data processed (2022)

Is a model 1 regression test that tests the influence of the Independent Variable Information System (X) on the Internet Facility variable (Z). The test results show the significant value of the Information System (X) = 0.00. It can be concluded that the information system has a significant effect on user satisfaction. The amount of R2 or R square value is 0.506, which means that the contribution given from the information system (X) variable analyzed to internet facilities was 50.6% and the remaining 49.4% was a contribution from other variables that were not analyzed in this study. The T value calculated for the implementation of the personnel information system was 8.155 > F table (1.99714). So it can be concluded that the implementation of information systems partially affects Internet facilities. The calculated F value of 66.502 with a significance value of 0.000, has the meaning that the information system affects user satisfaction.

Variable	B	Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
Information System	1.116	0.283	3.932	0.000
Internet Facility	1.131	0.325	3.477	0.001
Dependent Variable	= User satisfaction			
Constanta	= 18.394			
R	= 0.749			
R square (R ²)	= 0.560			
F	29.757			
Probability	0.000			
Line Equation I	Z = Py1X1 + Py1Z1+ e			
Result	Z = 0.283 + 0.325 + e			

Table 2: - Regression Model 2
Source: data processed (2022)

The table above shows the significance value of Information System (X) = 0.000, Internet facility (Z) = 0.001. So it can be concluded that Information systems and Internet Facilities have a significant effect on user satisfaction. The T value of the calculation of the implementation of the personnel information system is 3.932 > F table (1.99714), and the T value of the calculation of internet facilities is 3.477 > F table (1.99714). It can be concluded that the simultaneous implementation of information systems and internet facilities affects user satisfaction. The magnitude of the coefficient of determination is shown by the *summary* model, with an R square value of 0.560 or 56.0% which indicates the magnitude of the contribution of the influence of information system variables and internet facilities on user satisfaction variables, while the remaining 44% is the magnitude of the influence of other variables that were not studied in this study. In the results of the model 1 regression output, a calculated F value of 29.757 and a significance value of 0.000, means that the implementation of the staffing information system and internet facilities together affect user satisfaction.

Variable	Direct Effect	Sig.	Indirect Effect	Total Effect	Description
System information implementation–User Satisfaction	1.116	0.000			Significant
System information implementation – Internet facility	0.539	0.000			Significant
Internet facility – User satisfaction	1.131	0.001			Significant
System information satisfaction – Internet facility – User Satisfaction	1.116		1.116*1.131 =1.262	2.378	Significant

Table 3:- Rekapitulasi Hasil Analisis Jalur
Source: data diproses (2022)

Based on the table above, it has an indirect influence on the variables of the implementation of the personnel information system through internet facilities on user satisfaction. Furthermore, to determine the status of the mediation variable, it is formulated with the following conditions: 1) The *intervening* variable is considered to have

➤ *Path Analysis Test*

Path analysis in this study was carried out to calculate the direct and indirect influences of free variables (independent) and bound variables (dependent). Path analysis in this study was carried out to identify the path of the cause of a particular variable against other variables affected by the value of the coefficient and the value of significance in table 1 and table 2. Then based on the regression test values, a path model can be arranged shown in figure 2.

Figure 2 shows the value of each of the lines of influence between variables with e1 = (√1 -0.506) of 0.702 or 70.2% and e2 = (√1 -0.560) of 0.663 or 66.3%. The value of the influence of information systems through internet facilities on user satisfaction is displayed in the following path analysis:

Figure 2:- Path Diagram Results

Based on the path diagram model in figure 2, each of the direct and indirect influences on each path and the total value of the path can be obtained, the results of the Information System (X) on User Satisfaction (Y) through the Internet Facility (Z) which is displayed in the recapitulation table of the following path analysis results:

influence or has the status of mediation if the value of the indirect influence is greater than the direct influence. 2) The *intervening* variable is considered to have no influence or has no status as mediation if the value of the indirect influence is less than the direct influence.

B. Discussion

Furthermore, based on the results of research testing, the discussion is as follows:

➤ *Definition of Implementation of personnel information systems, Internet Facilities, and User Satisfaction.*

The implementation of information systems is a combination of information technology and human activities to support operations and management. The information system serves to help data processing and convey information to its users based on calculations or a database that has been integrated into the information system. (Sukanto & Shalahuddin, 2015) According to (Laudon & Laudon, 2014) "Technically an information system is a series of interconnected components that have the function of collecting, managing, processing, storing and distributing information that is very useful to provide support to the decision-making process and control the company. The implementation of an information system supported by the internet can encourage the level of satisfaction of information system users is the emotional state of system users that is pleasant or unpleasant towards the information system. Users of systems with a high level of satisfaction show a positive attitude towards the use of their information systems. But on the contrary, users who do not have a sense of satisfaction with the information system will show a negative attitude towards the system he manages. (Akhmal et al., 2018). The implementation of the personnel information system has a way to improve internet facilities at PT Kemajuan Industrindo with 3 assessment indicators (accuracy, timelines, and relevance).

Research on internet facilities for employees can be measured through user satisfaction with the impact of internet facilities for companies, especially at PT Kemajuan Industrindo. Internet facilities have a way to improve internet facilities at PT Kemajuan Industrindo with 3 assessment indicators (*hosting, domain, and webserver*).

According to (Machmud, 2018) User satisfaction is the response generated by the user after the user uses the product. The user's attitude towards a product or service is a subjective criterion related to how much the user likes the product or service used. Research on information system user satisfaction for employees at PT Kemajuan Industrindo can be measured by 5 assessment indicators (*learnability, efficiency, memorability, error and safety, and satisfaction*).

➤ *Implementation of information systems to user satisfaction.*

Information systems are digital devices that companies can use to build leading digital communications with a combination of transactions and data processing. Information systems can encourage the distribution of information in a company to run more efficiently. The implementation of the personnel information system is one of the stages for the company to make the information system function more optimally, with the implementation of the company's information system, it can find out how much the company's employees are satisfied in the operation of the information system instilled by the company, especially at PT Kemajuan

Industrindo. In this study, the assessment of the variables of the implementation of the personnel information system (x) was tested through 3 assessment indicators which consisted of three points: accuracy, timeliness, and relevance which were described in 12 points of statement in the questionnaire. The results were tested on 5 indicators of user satisfaction including:

Learnability, Efficiency, Memorability, Errors and safety, and Satisfaction were described in 17 statement points in the questionnaire.

Based on the test results using SPSS software in table 2, a sig value of 0.000 was obtained which is smaller than the alpha value of 0.005 (5%) so it can be concluded that there is a significant influence between the implementation of the staffing information system on user satisfaction. This research is in line with the previous research entitled Application of Information Systems in the Effect of Motivation on satisfaction and performance of the Ngawi Regency Financial Agency (Prasetyawan, 2021) which states that information systems have a significant effect on motivation, satisfaction, and performance. But motivation does not have a significant influence on performance. This shows that the existence of accuracy, punctuality, and relevance in the information system can affect the *learnability, Efficiency, Memorability, Errors and safety, and Satisfaction* of PT Kemajuan Industrindo employees.

➤ *Implementation of information systems for internet facilities*

Information systems can be embedded in internet facilities in companies. With the implementation of the staffing information system, internet facilities can provide more benefits for their users. An internet facility without the implementation of an information system can only be used as an entertainment medium, with the implementation of an information system in internet facilities, the internet can provide more valuable benefits for companies or organizations in data transactions, data processing, and data recapitulation, especially in meeting the needs of Information Technology in the development of internet facilities at PT Kemajuan Industrindo. In this study, the implementation of the personnel information system was able to increase the value of internet facilities at PT Kemajuan Industrindo. The assessment of the variables of the implementation of the personnel information system (x) was tested through 3 assessment indicators according to (Raymond McLeod, 2001) which consisted of three points: accuracy, timeliness, and relevance which were described in 12 points of statement in the questionnaire. The results were tested on 3 indicators of internet facilities according to (Iqbal Kurniansyah & Sinurat, 2020) including *Hosting, Domain and Webserver* which were described as 11 points of statement in the questionnaire.

Based on the test results using SPSS software in table 1, a sig value of 0.000 was obtained which is smaller than the alpha value of 0.005 (5%) so it can be concluded that there is a significant influence between the implementation of the staffing information system on internet facilities. This research is in line with previous research conducted by (Chen

& Lin, 2019) entitled *Exploration and Implementation of Intelligent Park System Based on Cloud Computing and Internet of Things* the research states that Information Systems can realize interconnection and communication between communication terminal devices and can increase efficiency between systems. This shows that the existence of accuracy, punctuality, and relevance in an information system can affect the selection of hosting, domain, and web server selection at PT Kemajuan Industrindo Malang.

➤ *Internet facilities for user satisfaction*

Along with the development of information technology, internet facilities are an important means for companies to accelerate the process of distributing information and communication to increase productivity for companies, especially at PT Kemajuan Industrindo. The assessment of internet facility variables (z) was tested through 3 assessment indicators according to (Iqbal Kurniansyah & Sinurat, 2020) including *Hosting, Domains, and Webservers* which were described as 11 points of statement in the questionnaire. The results were tested on 5 indicators of user satisfaction according to (Handiwidjojo & Ernawati, 2016) including *Learnability, Efficiency, Memorability, Errors and safety, and Satisfaction* which were described as 17 points of statement in the questionnaire.

Based on the test results using SPSS software in table 2, a sig value of 0.001 was obtained which is smaller than the alpha value of 0.005 (5%) so it can be concluded that there is a significant influence on the implementation of the staffing information system on user satisfaction. This research is in line with the previous research entitled *Internet use and job satisfaction* (Castellacci & Viñas-Bardolet, 2019) which states that internet technology can increase satisfaction by increasing access to data and information, the internet can create new activities and can facilitate communication and social interaction. This shows that the existence of *hosting, domains, and web servers* can affect the *learnability, efficiency, memorability, errors and safety, and satisfaction* of PT Kemajuan Industrindo employees.

➤ *Implementation of information systems to user satisfaction through internet facilities*

To keep up with the development of the world of technology and to provide fast information, the implementation of the personnel information system through internet facilities is now an important factor for companies, internet facilities in the company will be more up-to-date with the implementation of information systems in it that can increase satisfaction for information system users, especially for PT Kemajuan Industrindo. In this study, internet facilities had a significant effect as a mediation variable between the influence of the implementation of the staffing information system in influencing user satisfaction. Based on table 3, the value of the indirect influence (implementation of the personnel information system on user satisfaction through internet facilities) is obtained greater than the direct influence (implementation of the personnel information system on user satisfaction).

This research is in line with the previous research entitled *The Impact of Cloud-Based Information Systems Organization's Performance* (Algrari, 2017), which stated that cloud-based Information Systems have a large role in the value of organizational performance. The value can be seen based on the improvement in the information system processes indicated by the performance of the organization. This shows that the implementation of an information system with good quality of accuracy, punctuality, and relevance with the existence of internet facilities in which it has good hosting quality, domains, and web servers, can increase the satisfaction of information system users who have been assessed from the ability of system users to learn the system, provide efficiency values, optimize memory in operating information systems, troubleshooting problems in *errors* and creating a sense of security and providing convenience for users. With the improvement of information systems and internet facilities, the satisfaction of information system users at PT Kemajuan Industrindo will increase.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research and discussion of the results of testing the effect of the implementation of the personnel information system on user satisfaction through internet facilities at PT Kemajuan Industrindo and supported by several theories, it can be concluded that as follows:

- The implementation of the Personnel Information System is one of the stages for the company to make the information system function more optimally, with the implementation of the personnel information system through internet facilities, the company can find out how much employees are satisfied with operating the information system, the distribution of information data and the accuracy of the data presented by the company's personnel information system at PT Kemajuan Industrindo. The implementation of information systems can be measured through the level of accuracy, timeliness, and relevance of data distribution. Internet facilities can be measured through the quality of hosting, domains, and web servers used by the company. For information systems, user satisfaction can be measured through learnability, efficiency, memorability, error and safety, and satisfaction.
- The implementation of the personnel information system is an activity carried out by the company to provide information to employees of PT Kemajuan Industrindo regarding staffing data needed by all employees of PT Kemajuan Industrindo. The implementation of the personnel information system at PT Kemajuan Industrindo has been running well and must be maintained and improved in terms of accuracy, punctuality, and relevance so that employees of PT Kemajuan Industrindo will increasingly feel comfortable and satisfied with the implementation of the personnel information system.
- The implementation of the personnel information system has an important role in the use of internet facilities at PT Kemajuan Industrindo Malang. The Implementation Stage of the Personnel Information System in an internet facility requires high accuracy so that the system can continue to function optimally, in addition, as a follow-up

plan to maintain quality in the Implementation of the Personnel Information System in internet facilities, a maintenance, and maintenance process is needed that is carried out periodically to continue to provide good and optimal performance for employees of PT Kemajuan Industrindo Malang.

- Internet facilities are a means that can be used to increase user satisfaction. With internet facilities, employees can find information and data more easily at work or fill their free time when resting. With the existence of optimal internet facilities in the selection of hosting, domains and web servers and accompanied by good service from internet providers, it will further increase the satisfaction of PT Kemajuan Industrindo employees as internet facility users.
- The implementation of an information system can be done through internet facilities to achieve user satisfaction. With the existence of internet facilities, information systems can facilitate the process of distributing data and information, internet facilities can strengthen the impression of transparency of staffing information systems for companies to their employees. The implementation of information systems supported by internet facilities must be maintained and improved in terms of hosting, domain, and web server selection. Along with the development of technology, the higher the specifications of internet facilities can make the system able to run more optimally so that employees will feel more comfortable and satisfied in operating the information system, especially at PT Kemajuan Industrindo.

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